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Training Handbook for ESRs

Revised 11.2015

Training Plan

Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
H2020-MSCA-ITN-2014
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

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Digital Chain

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Training Plan

Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this task:
CITA

innochain

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Introduction

Dear ESR, welcome to the Innochain training network. This document serves as your basic introduction to Innochain and aims to guide you through the project, the collaborations and the training programme. The document is a dynamic document and will be revised runningly.

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Innochain is an Innovative Training Network under the EU Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions. It creates a shared research training environment examining how advances in digital design tools challenge building culture enabling more sustainable, more informed and more materially smart design solutions.

With a strong inter-sector focus, Innochain connects “research in practice” with “research in academia”. Assembling 6 internationally recognised academic research environments leading research into computational design in architecture and engineering and 14 innovation pioneering industry partners from architecture, engineering, design software development and fabrication, the programme is a shared training platform for 15 early stage

*Image left
Transmissive Assemblies,
Milling pattern, CITA*

researchers (ESR). The structured training programme focusses on supervision of individual research projects, an inter-sector secondment programme as well as collective research events including workshop-seminars, colloquia, summer school and research courses providing the unique opportunity to obtain new knowledge and skills positioned between strong innovative research practice and influential industrial impact.

Topic

The programme investigates the extended digital chain as a particular opportunity for interdisciplinary design collaboration. Challenging the traditional thinking of design as a linear process of incremental refinement, InnoChain identifies three axes of design innovation potential communication, simulation and materialisation appearing as distributed and interdisciplinary activities across the design chain. Situating feedback between design processes as a key concern for developing holistic and integrated design methods, the network will develop new interdisciplinary design methods that integrate advanced simulation and interface with material fabrication.

The three axes define the three central scientific work packages:

- *Communicating Design*
- *Simulation for Design*
- *Materialising Design*

The work packages are means by which the network research is coordinated and organised allowing for inter-project and cross-institutional collaboration. Each ESR has an established role within one of these three work packages.

WP3 Communicating Design	1	Evy Slabbinck	Designing Isogeometric Analysis	ITKE	BIG	McNeel
	2	Tom Svillans	Integrating Material Performance	CITA	Bluhmer Lehmann	White
	3	Angelos Chronis	Building Physics for Performance Control	IAAC	McNeel	Foster+
	4	Zeynep Aksoz	Multi-criteria Optimisation in Early Design Phase	IOA	str.ucture	BIG
	5	Dimitrie A. Stefanescu	Alternate means to Communicate Measure	BSA	HENN	HENN
WP4 Simulating for Design	6	Paul Poinet	Multi Scalar Modelling for Building Design	CITA	Buro Happold	designtoproduction
	7	Christoph Hermann	Simulating Anisotropic Material	IOA	Cloud 9	Bluhmer Lehman
	8	James Solly	Virtual Prototyping FRP	ITKE	S-Form	Foster+
	9	Vasily Sitnikov	Simulating concrete formwork	KTH	Buro Happold	Buro Happold
	10	Giulio Brugnaro	Simulating robotic feedback	BSA	ROK-Office	BIG
WP5 Materialising Design	11	Helena Westerlind	Concrete Printing	KTH	Factum Arte	White
	12	Saman Saffarian	Material Gradient FRP	ITKE	Str-ucture	S-Form
	13	Arthur Prior	Applied robotics - Controlled Material Deposition	BSA	Foster+	Buro Happold.
	14	Kasper Ax	Design for Manufacture and Assembly	CITA	designtoproduction	Bluhmer Lehmann
	15	Stephanie Chaltiel	Small scale robotic manufacturing for large scale	IAAC	Cloud 9	ROK-Office

Structure

The shared training programme aims to develop a highly profiled learning environment through which you will learn to:

- Think in an interdisciplinary way allowing design decisions to be informed by an integrated and holistic understanding of the building design process.
- Develop situated solutions that creatively tie building design research to application in context
- Invent new creative design methods for a sustainable and materially smart architecture
- Network with science, industry and other regulatory stakeholders in the building industry
- Transfer knowledge from associated disciplines as new innovation potential for better building

The training takes 5 forms: **1) the individual research project, 2) secondments with industry partners, 3) scientific training and 4) transferrable skills training**, including workshop-seminars, summer school and research courses. Further **5) evaluation events** in the form of colloquia and evaluation seminars allow the network to track progress and give you feedback.

All 6 academic beneficiaries (institutions) contribute to the research and training programme. ESR research is distributed across the 6 beneficiaries and training activities are shared across the network. This equal involvement in the research and training tasks supports and preserves the interdisciplinary nature of the project.

The key stone of the network is the **individual research project** and its link to the secondment programme. It is through the individual research project that the ESR is en

gaged in the overarching research question, supervised by an expert in the field and interfaced the industrial research partners. The individual research project is placed within one of the three sub-tracks. Each sub-track is composed of 5 ESRs from different institutions and disciplines. The 3 sub-tracks allow for further focussed research

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exchanges and collaboration and enable additional synergy. The supervision of the individual research projects takes place within the research environments of the academic beneficiaries and the industrial partners. As such, an ESR has two primary research contexts to which the individual research project belongs.

The **secondments** are structured research collaborations with the industry partners. Each ESR is expected to undertake two 4-month secondments with either a single or two strategically paired industry partners (in total 22%). The industry collaborations are planned and the collaboration ensured by the network. We understand that building practice is dynamic. For the secondment programme to work we expect the secondments to be flexibly implemented. We will support you in establishing continuous relationships to your industry partners so you can engage with their changing project opportunities and deadlines.

*Images above
DevA, CITA, Bartlett workshops
and robotic weaving, Bartlett*

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Beyond the individual research project and the industry collaboration Innochain collaborates to create a **training programme** consisting of workshop-seminars, summer school, scientific research courses and transferrable skills courses. While some of these courses are optional others are required. As a means of planning your project you are expected to develop an **ESR Research, Training and Career Plan** in which you outline the guiding research question for your individual research project, the role, content, structure and timing of your industry secondments, your participation in scientific training, transferrable skills training and evaluation events.

Finally, you are expected to take part in the network's **dissemination plan** including the three key research exhibitions, the network journal and the log book.

*Image above
Umbrella prototype investigation, structure*

Appointment and enrolment

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Each ESR is appointed for 36 months. This is the maximum research time the network can support. Through your appointment you are each contracted through the individual institutions giving you equal opportunities with your local colleagues. This also means that your appointments will be different from institution to institution given the specific regulation in the country where your institution is located.

Through your enrolment as a PhD-student a second agreement, **The Researcher Agreement**, is appended to your contract and outlines the expectations and requirements of the Innochain network and in alignment with national regulation for PhD-education. At the point of writing The Researcher Agreement still needs to be implemented. It is your local beneficiary that chooses how to use the given EU funding to financially support your research including travel, accommodation, conference attendance etc).

Method

Innochain shares an experimental research-by-design methodology focussing on design-led physical experimentation and full scale prototyping. The emphasis on **the design and implementation of material design experiments** allows the programme to engage directly with the investigated techniques and technologies moving along the digital chain from design and analysis to specification and fabrication. This integrated approach positions the research inquiries within a similar network of interconnected expertise and practice that make up architectural and engineering design practice. The material experiments generate shared empirical data that can be tested, analysed and evaluated by the research teams across the network and ensures that results can be appropriated and implemented within the industrial partnership.

Scientifically, the physical experiments act as material research inquiries by which the concepts and technologies of the research inquiries are evaluated. The method is relevant for design-led research in architecture and engineering as it ties design creativity to research investi-

*Image left
CNC milling of large scale
building element, Blumer
Lehmann*

gation. To employ a research-by-design methodology allows the individual research projects to engage with the solution-led processes of creative trouble-shooting that characterise the design process.

The programme identifies three kinds of material evidence:

- Speculative design probes allowing ideation
- Material prototyping enabling direct full scale testing of defined design criteria against real-world methods of realisation and production
- Demonstrators acting as proof-of-concept testing design criteria in direct spatial manners

The three kinds of evidence are seen as sequential and iterative design phases building up the complexity of the project while addressing different contexts of re-search thinking. The research method places the exhibitions as central research instruments. Beyond acting as a means of public dissemination, the research exhibitions are milestones by which research results are produced, tested and evaluated.

*Image above
SForm, Kiledar Forrest, Bartlett,
2011 research pavilion ICD/
ITKE.*

Training programme

The training programme consists of 5 forms of research training. All training is coordinated and organised as part of Work Package 2 Training and as part of the three scientific Work Packages:

- Work Package 3: Communicating Design
- Work Package 4: Simulation for Design
- Work Package 5: Materialising Design

Training is measured in ECTS points, a shared European scale. You are expected to participate in 30 ECTS points worth of training. 1 ECTS point equals 25 work hours. Each training event is allocated a particular number of points.

1) The individual research project

The 15 ESR's **individual research projects** are the key-stone in the research network. It is through the individual research that the ESR is engaged in the research question, supervised by an expert in the field and interfaced the

*Image left
FE analysis of ITKE/ICD re-
search pavillion 2011, ITKE*

industrial research partners. The individual research project is placed within one of the three project sub-tracks (Work Package 3: Communicating Design Work Package 4, Simulation for Design and Work Package 5 Materialising Design). Each sub-track is composed of 5 ESRs from different institutions and disciplines. The 3 sub-tracks allow for further focussed research exchanges and collaboration and enable additional synergy.

The supervision of the individual research projects takes place within the research environments of the academic beneficiaries and the industrial partners. As such, an ESR has two primary research contexts to which the individual research project belongs. To support supervision, expand exposure and ensure continuity in reviewing ESRs are offered academic co-supervision by a beneficiary other than the host institution within the network. This secondary supervisor will give individual supervision, be present at colloquia presentation and take part in the pre-viva and final viva exam. This ensures continuity and supports general supervision across the individual research projects.

2) Secondments

The secondment programme is the central instrument for inter-sector collaboration and exchange. Each ESR is expected to undertake two 4-month secondments with either a single or two strategically paired industry partners (in total 22% of research time). The secondments take place with central industrial partners that hold particular expertise in the research field and allow the ESRs to understand their research question in context of direct application and implementation.

The primary tool for integration is the **embedded design project**. Employing the design-led experimental method, ESRs will work on existing industrial design projects and situate, develop and implement their research using the project to understand design criteria and resistances, create scope and trouble shoot solutions. The embedded design project is supported by the experimental research method and allows ESRs to develop their individual research projects in context of industry practice meaning that results will be relevant and easily transferable for implementation.

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The industry collaborations are planned and the collaboration ensured by the network. We understand that building practice is highly dynamic. For the secondment programme to work we expect the secondments to be flexibly implemented. This will be secured firstly through a flexible secondment staging in which the secondment periods can be changed to fit with industrial projects and secondly through the individual ESR secondment logbook and bi-monthly industrial supervision sessions which communicates results continually to the industrial partners and the network as a whole. The supervisor will sup-

*Image above
Endesa Pavilion Solar House
2.0, IAAC*

3) Scientific training

The scientific training uses two core research instruments: the workshop-seminar and the research course. The workshop-seminar is a dual training event combining a hands-on workshop in which particular methods and tools are shared with a contextualising seminar with expert presentations. The workshop-seminars link to the 3 sub-tracks and hold a particular industry focus. The research courses include both technology focussed courses allowing ESRs the necessary skills to creatively and critically engage with technology as well as theoretical courses that allow contextualisation. The research courses will be provided by the academic partners across the 6 institutions and will be open for all ESRs. Both the scientific training and the transferable skills training programme include optional and required events.

4) Transferable skills training courses

The transferable skills training focusses on implementation and innovation. They include project management, entrepreneurship and IP as well as personal career planning helping ESRs to envisage career paths that cross disciplines and sectors and an incubator programme focussing on start-ups and business building. To support transferable skill development with special focus on innovation development two industrial partners hold further training responsibility. HENN will develop and host the interdisciplinary summer school “Drivers of Innovation” and Smith Innovation will develop and run the research courses “Innovation in Practice” and “Incubator Programme”.

*Images above
design2production with
Holzbau Amann. Centre
Pompidou, Metz.
Architect: Shigeru Ban*

5) Evaluation events

Evaluative training events: Research Colloquia and VIVA presentations are central in gathering the network, reviewing progress and creating exchange. The two colloquia are strategically placed at the end of the first and second ESR training year acting as evaluation events in which research progress is assessed and scientific quality assured. ESRs present their research to the academic and industrial partners as well as invited researchers that peer-review research questions, methodologies and results. The pre-viva presentation assembles the three sub-tracks allowing for focussed conversations and strategic feedback enabling ESRs to develop strong write-up plans. Invited researchers review progress and contextualise results. The final viva exam will take place in the hosting institutions following local PhD rules for PhD examination. The colloquia are paralleled with three research exhibitions show-casing experimental results in the form of speculative design probes, material prototypes and demonstrators and positioning material research as effective parts of the research enquiries.

*Image above
Transmissive Assemblages, ceiling panels, CITA*

Expectations of the ESR

Innochain's ESRs are expected to :

1. Carry out an individual research project resulting in a thesis
2. Take part in the secondment programme
3. Develop and carry out a detailed ESR Research, Training and Career Plan
4. Participate in the Innochain's training, evaluation and dissemination programme and participate in the required events
5. Fulfil the requirements of their institution's PhD school
6. Help organise the workshop-seminars, summer school and/or conference
7. Help organise the exhibitions, network journals and on occasion take the lead of the network social media account
8. Present minimum two papers at international conferences, write two network journal articles, and write in different genres (e.g. social media)
9. Communicate the development of the individual research project through a log book on innochain.net
10. Create minimum 1 video entry for innochain.net

The ESR Research, Training and Career Plan is an individual research plan for the single ESR. It is a dynamic document which will be amended and changed over the course of the research project. It should be authored by the ESR and discussed and agreed with the beneficiary supervisor (academic supervisor) and industry supervisor.

The ESR Research, Training and Career Plan should:

- present a plan for the research including the research question, method and overview of key state of the art references
- define the role of the industry collaboration and secondment programme
- outline anticipation for results to be showcased in the three research exhibitions: Speculative Design Probes, Material Prototypes and Demonstrators
- declare participation in Scientific Training Programme including required courses
- declare participation in Transferable Skills Training Programme including required courses
- develop a career plan (this will be further supported in the career plan course)
- outline a time plan in the format of a gantt chart
- The ESR Research, Training and Career Plan should be presented at Start Up seminar in March 2016
- outline a plan for dissemination in accordance with the expectations outlined in bullet 1-10

Expectations of the beneficiary

Over all the beneficiaries are expected to support the implementation of the actions outlined in the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement for Innochain. Of specific relevance for the ESR's beneficiaries are expected to:

1. appoint ESRs under an employment contract (or other direct contract with equivalent benefits, including social security coverage) or — if not otherwise possible under national law — under a fixed amount fellowship agreement with minimum social security coverage due to national regulation
2. advise ESR of the administrative regulations of the grant
3. support ESR in developing independent research project through
 - making available a strong research environment with track record in the given area of research and support synergy between the independent research project and existing projects
 - supervise ESR in the development of the project
 - support and supervise the industry collaborations including the secondment programme
 - support and supervise the ESRs involvement in Innochain's training, evaluation and dissemination programme
 - take part in evaluation events providing feedback on scientific standing and project progress
 - support and enable access to available workshops and toolsets where necessary to the research

Expectations of the industry partner

Industry partners are expected to support and contribute to the implementation of the activities initiated by the Innochain network as described in the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement for the network.

Of special relevance for the ESR's the industry partners are expected to:

- making available a strong research environment with track record in the given area of research and support synergy between the independent research project and existing projects
- co-supervise the ESRs in their individual research projects and be in dialogue with
- host secondments
- enable ESRs to situate and apply their research findings through embedded design projects
- take part in evaluation events providing feedback on scientific standing and project progress
- support and enable access to available workshops and toolsets where necessary to the research
- support the dissemination activities of the research project

Overview of scientific, transferrable skills training and evaluation events

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The following list outlines the evaluation, scientific training and transferrable skills training courses included in the Innochain training programme. It is also explained which of the courses are required for the Innochain ESRs.

	Main Training Events & Conferences	ECTS	Lead Institution	Required	Project Mth
#	EVALUATION EVENTS				
2	First year colloquium & exhibition "Design Probes"	-	IOA	X	18
3	Second year colloquium & exhibition "Prototypes"	-	IAAC	X	30
4	Pre viva seminar: strategic feedback for strong write-up plans.	-	ITKE	X	36
5	Final exam (VIVA)	-	All beneficiaries	X	42
28	Final conference & exhibition "Demonstrators"	-	CITA	X	45

Evaluation events

The evaluation events are central in gathering the network, reviewing progress and creating exchange. The **two colloquia** are strategically placed at the end of the first and second ESR training year acting as evaluation events in which research progress is assessed and scientific quality assured. ESRs present their research to the academic and industrial partners as well as invited researchers that peer-review research questions, methodologies and results. The **pre-viva presentation** assembles the three sub-tracks allowing for focussed conversations and strategic feedback enabling ESRs to develop strong write-up plans. Invited researchers review progress and contextualise results. The **final viva evaluation** will take place in the hosting institutions following local PhD rules for PhD examination.

The colloquia are paralleled with **three research exhibitions** show-casing experimental results in the form of speculative design probes, material prototypes and demonstrators and positioning material research as effective parts of the research enquiries.

Course #	Main Training Events & Conferences	ECTS	Lead Institution	Required	Project Mth
	SCIENTIFIC TRAINING EVENTS				
1	Start-up seminar: Introduces the network theme and academic and industrial partners and ESRs. Presents the 3 sub tracks and develops axes of synergy between projects.	1	CITA		7
12	Sci Course: Theory of Computation and Technology: Contextualises employed computational strategies and associated technologies for digital fabrication through an interdisciplinary understanding of the driving theories	3.5	BSA		9
16	Sci Course: Robotic steering and control: Introduces robotic control protocols for design based interfacing. With special focus on new interfacing tools for intuitive robot-CAD interfacing. The course will facilitate fundamental skills necessary in sub-track3: materialisation.	1.5	IAAC		10
14	Sci Course: Computation: Introduces ESRs to contemporary digital design methods. Special emphasis will be put on the successful interaction of digital design and production technology. Current developments and technologies will be analysed and discussed.	1.5	IOA		11
6	Workshop-seminar 1.1 Communication design. Introducing light weight simulation tools for early stage design structural ideation. Presents a hands-on training environment where participants work directly with CAD interfaced spring-based modelling exploring feedback between material behaviour and architectural-structural design. The workshop is contextualised by a seminar with invited researchers reviewing workshop results and presenting examples of simulation driven design.	1.5	CITA	X (for those in the specified work packages)	12
7	Workshop-seminar 1.2 Simulating design: Identifying the relevance of accurate simulation tools within the context of design and building industry. Presents the foundational elements of state of the art analysis methods through a hands-on workshop with CAD interfaced FE simulation tools. The workshop is contextualised by a seminar with invited researchers reviewing results and presenting examples of FE integrated design solutions.	1.5	ITKE	X (for those in the specified work packages)	12
8	Workshop-seminar 1.3 Materialising design: identifying critical concepts and drives of robotic fabrication. Presents concepts for additive fabrication in building practice. Employing an industrial robot, the workshop allows participants to design for and programme fabrication. The workshop is contextualised by a seminar with invited researchers reviewing results and presenting examples of implemented robotic fabrication in building design.	1.5	BSA	X (for those in the specified work packages)	12
13	Sci Course: Methodology and experiment. Introduces ESRs to established research methodologies with a focus on experimentation and the inclusion of material evidence. The course presents, discusses and critically reviews methods employed in research-by-design and parallel these with interdisciplinary methods from engineering and physical science in which experimentation is central.	2	CITA		15
18	Sci Course: Simulation: Introduces virtual simulations of load bearing, aesthetic and ecological behaviour of architectural envelopes and structural systems. Presents interdisciplinary, systematic methods for experimenting, testing and evaluating design.	1.5	IOA		18
15	Sci Course: Material Design: Introduces advanced topics in the field of material design and simulation technology. The course delivers necessary knowledge to successfully engage in the application of advanced materials in design and engineering. Simulation and analysis tools and the measurement of material properties and behaviour will also play a key role to critically understand the limits and potentials associated to advanced material design.	1.5	ITKE		20
9	Workshop-seminar 2.1 Communicating design: Identifying methods for interdisciplinary collaboration. The workshop presents key problems of interdisciplinary collaboration that characterise working across the digital chain. It presents tools for shared prototyping and hybrid modelling enabling the integration of domain specific knowledge into common design platforms. The workshop is contextualised by a seminar with invited researchers reviewing results and presenting examples of collaborative processes.	1.5	KTH	X (for those in the specified work packages)	24
10	Workshop-seminar 2.2 Simulating design: Introducing virtual prototyping strategies and for new material practice. Presents multiple strategies from neighbouring fields allowing participants to engage the different phases of design specification, prototyping and fabrication in practice resulting in full scale prototypes. The workshop is contextualised by a seminar with invited researchers review projects and present examples of virtual prototyping driven fabrication.	1.5	IOA	X (for those in the specified work packages)	24
11	Workshop-seminar 2.3 Materialising design: Introducing novel materials for robotically steered fabrication. Presents different materials (clay, plaster, vary concrete mixes) for robotic fabrication and allows participants to explore how their formal and structural performances interact with the fabrication-based requirements. The workshop is contextualised by a seminar with invited researchers reviewing results and presenting examples of experimental material fabrication.	1.5	IAAC	X (for those in the specified work packages)	24

Scientific training events

The scientific training events uses two core research instruments: the workshop-seminar and the research course. The workshop-seminar is a dual training event combining a hands-on workshop in which particular methods and tools are shared with a contextualising seminar with expert presentations. The workshop-seminars link to the 3 sub-tracks and hold a particular industry focus. It is intended that ESRs only follow the Workshop-Seminars of their own sub-track.

The research courses include both technology focussed courses allowing ESRs the necessary skills to creatively and critically engage with technology as well as theoretical courses that allow contextualisation. The research courses will be provided by the academic partners across the 6 institutions and will be open for all ESRs

Course #	Main Training Events & Conferences	ECTS	Lead Institution	Required	Project Mth
	TRANSFERRABLE SKILLS COURSES				
20	TransferSkill Course: Dissemination, Communication, Networking and Peerreviewing. Introduces critical reflection through dissemination, reporting and paper writing. Supports key dissemination activities including the network journal and exhibitions.	3	All beneficiaries	X	14,20,26,32,38
26	Personal Career Development: the course is structured as a series of personal sessions with individual ESRs across the 36 months supporting idea of career opportunities and networking.	1	All beneficiaries	X	28,32,36,40
24	TransferSkill Course: Academic writing: sharpens the ESRs' awareness of the underlying structure and patterns of scientific and engineering research articles, and improves proficiency in writing up scientific research in English. ESRs' texts are peer-reviewed. Class preparation includes analysis of texts in the course material and exercises focusing on problematic areas for academic writing for scientists and engineers.	3	KTH		10
25	Summer school "Drivers of Innovation": Introduces interdisciplinary models for innovation. The summer school is hands-on participatory training environment allowing ESRs to situate their own research in innovation-based development processes. The summer school invites a broad assembly of innovators from related industries such as the car manufacture and industrial design to present their practice and experiences and discuss how innovation is brought about, what are the drivers and how can we positively affect development.	3	HENN	X	16
21	TransferSkill Course: Project Management: Training ESRs in project management skills and interdisciplinary communication for the building industry. Introduces the central processes and tools including planning, coordination, execution and assessment methods fundamental to both academic and professional research.	1.5	ITKE		17
22	TransferSkill Course: IP and Law: is a course on how to create successful innovations. The key take-away is an understanding of the road from a research result to a product or a service on the market. This will make the ESRs more successful in their professional lives regardless of which career path they choose.	2	KTH		22
23	TransferSkill Course: Innovation in Practice: Introduces critical and practical tools for innovation thinking focussing on diverse ways of implementing innovation in practice through technological innovation, process innovation and service innovation. The course is specially tailored to the InnoChain network defining innovation potential in respect to design methodology.	2	Smith Innovation	X	25
27	Incubator programme: connects ESRs to experienced practitioners from the industry partnership to discuss start-up potential, identify critical stages in business planning, funding and business growth.	1	Smith Innovation	X	36

Transferrable skills courses

The transferrable skills courses focusses on implementation and innovation. They include project management, entrepreneurship and IP as well as personal career planning helping ESRs to envisage career paths that cross disciplines and sectors and an incubator programme focusing on start-ups and business building. The central event will be the **summer school “Drivers of Innovation”** hosted by industrial partner HENN.

Gantt chart of events

R = ESR Start Date: ESRs will be contracted within the first 6 months allowing for homogeneity in the group and enable transferability in results, timely sharing of relevant courses, synergy and exchange. Some allowance is given for ESRs pers

S = Secondment Secondments are initially planned as above. However, the research model of the embedded design project necessitates running collaboration and flexible secondment planning (see 2.2.2). It is therefore anticipated that ESRs m

K= Kick off meeting

E = End of project

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